

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITION OF PEDAGOGICAL TOLERANCE AND APPROACHES IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In this article, professional tolerance, its components, the need to develop pedagogical tolerance, specific aspects of pedagogical tolerance, approaches to the development of professional tolerance, components of professional tolerance, the content of pedagogical tolerance, differences between tolerance and tolerance, tolerance, the specific aspects of each of them opinions of experts, the content of research on the development of pedagogical tolerance are discussed. The article serves as a scientific resource for the scientific-pedagogical community, students, professors, teachers, and researchers.*

Keywords: *tolerance, professional tolerance, cognitive, emotional, behavioral, tolerant approach, existential-humanistic, diversified, personal, dialogue-based, facilitative, pedagogue, future teacher.*

The organization of higher pedagogical education based on the humanistic paradigm implies the provision of personal and professional development of future teachers. Because the future teacher develops in the educational process as a subject of his life activity. The existence of different regional approaches to this problem encourages specialists to conduct regular research. In this process, it is of particular importance to determine the means of improving the professional activity of the future teacher. Because these tools are important in professional training of future teachers. A number of problems are encountered in the process of successful implementation of the goal of training future teachers. The biggest problem is the lack of motivation to become a teacher among students admitted to higher pedagogical educational institutions. As a result, it can be seen that the professional competences of young teachers who started working in general secondary schools are insufficiently developed. To overcome these problems, it is required to develop professional tolerance in future teachers.

Pedagogical tolerance is a component of general tolerance. Based on the historical experience of the Uzbek people, the essence of tolerance is approached in a unique way. Because tolerance has different meanings. From a philosophical point of view, the concept of tolerance - (lat. Tolerance - endurance, patience) tolerance - means to be tolerant and resistant to the way of life, behavior, habits, feelings, opinions, ideas and beliefs of others.[2] From the pedagogical point of view, tolerance, that is, tolerance, is a term that represents people who have moral qualities such as kindness, caring, generosity, generosity towards others. Tolerance means respecting other people's worldview, religious beliefs, national and ethnic affiliation, characteristics, traditions, not allowing discrimination and insults in dealings, considering humanity above all else, and observing it in the community, workplace, and neighborhood.[1] It can be seen that the words expressing the concepts of tolerance and tolerance are interpreted as synonyms. Tolerance refers to the quality of a person who tolerates what.

A. Lektorsky interprets talent in four directions:

1. Tolerance as indifference
2. Tolerance is the impossibility of mutual understanding

3. Tolerance as mercy

4. Tolerance as an expansion of personal experience and critical dialogue.

In psychological research, there is an approach to tolerance as social relations or social norms. L.G.Pochebut defines tolerance as follows: "Tolerance is unpleasant or a non-violent way of relating to strangers". M.S.Matskovsky expresses the following opinion about tolerance: "Tolerance determines the quality of certain relations between objects and subjects, in this process it is understood that the subjects are ready to accept the socio-cultural characteristics of the objects, to understand the specific aspects of their behavior." N.V.Nedorezova also approached tolerance in a unique way: "Tolerance is interpreted as a social institution, it covers three components as a specific direction, which are behavioral, emotional and cognitive states." O.A.Kharlamova commented on tolerance and noted the following: "tolerance represents the attitude of a person to a group of people, society and each other, it is manifested as humility and acceptance."

In a word, tolerance means the form of attitude expressed to others, the tolerant acceptance of various things and cultural models that do not correspond to one's own. As we mentioned above, experts have also distinguished between the concepts of tolerance and tolerance. R.Safarova, G.Akramova, R.Medetova used the concepts of tolerance and tolerance as synonyms, while E.Yu.Kleptsova tried to define the border between them. According to him, the leading mechanism of tolerance is tolerance.

Fortitude means self-control, self-control, and self-control. All this allows you to be sensitive to unfavorable factors. As a result of the use of other mechanisms, the tolerance becomes secondary. As the leading mechanism of tolerance, efforts to accept something are shown. Among them is empathy, understanding, determination. For the future teacher, it is important to develop tolerance as well as tolerance.

Pedagogical tolerance approaches are expressed to a certain extent in T.P. Skrikina's research. He interpreted tolerance as related to trust. When thinking about interaction with another person, trust refers to the internal willingness of subjects to interact. They do not simply enter each other's intellectual-value spheres, in which one person, including the teacher, does not simply accept the student, but treats him as a value, shares his values with him. According to T.P.Skrikina, tolerance is manifested as a mechanism of trust. This approach is important for pedagogical activity. Trust is important in a teacher's tolerant attitude toward students. With the help of trust, the teacher understands and shares the values, perspectives, and opinions of the students. On the other hand, tolerance is shown as a mechanism of communication between the teacher and the students. Tolerance, on the other hand, means not reacting or reducing it, not showing a clear expression of sensitivity to the situations that arise. A tolerant attitude towards anxiety is manifested through tolerance and self-control. Accordingly, tolerance is expressed as a defense mechanism in a situation of pressure and serves to ensure the psychological stability of a person. Therefore, mental stability and a friendly atmosphere are created among the students in the classes where teachers with the qualities of professional tolerance are working.

This interpretation of tolerance is important for the process of training future teachers. Because pedagogical activity requires the teacher to have a stable and tolerant attitude towards various pressures. Therefore, tolerance not only ensures that the teacher achieves high results in the process of pedagogical activity, but also has a special pedagogical value as a mechanism for protecting the mental health of students. It should be noted that tolerance cannot be equated with indifference and inactivity of the teacher.

According to A.G.Asmalova, tolerance is not only rational, but also a voluntary state, which is expressed in actions. The term tolerance embodies three interrelated concepts: stability, resilience; tolerance; acceptance.

S.L.Bratsenko put forward the following approaches to the study of the phenomenon of tolerance: existential-humanistic, diversification, personal, dialogue-based, facilitative approaches.

Within the framework of the existential-humanistic approach, tolerance is evaluated as a phenomenon that expresses the maturity of a person. A mature person means a person with a tolerant outlook. Tolerance also means a person's value and outlook on life. Tolerance has a specific meaning in each specific situation, and it requires searching for this meaning and making responsible decisions. Tolerance is a product of a humanitarian perspective, which is analyzed within the framework of human capabilities. This approach takes a special place in the manifestation of the individual's tolerance. The tolerance of the teacher is of particular importance in the process of person-oriented education. If the teacher cannot create a favorable pedagogical environment for the development of students, they will not have the ability to choose their individual life trajectories, think independently and creatively, express their views clearly, make life choices, and feel responsible for their decisions. In this process, the teacher's tolerance and personal example are important. First of all, the teacher himself should have a tolerant attitude towards the students and the people around him, he should be able to accept them as full-fledged subjects of the communication process. Only then tolerance is manifested as a professional quality of the teacher, a requirement for professional competence, a social pedagogical method. It is important that the teacher always understands why and for what purpose he can show professional tolerance.

Within the framework of the diversification approach, attention is paid to the multifaceted, colorful nature of tolerance. Experts who researched this approach to tolerance I.V.Krutova, V.A.Tishkova I.B.Grinspun, I.Shkuratova, V.I.Boyko, A.V.Pertsev, G.U.Soldatovas thought about its unique features and appearances. They justified the manifestation of many forms and aspects of pedagogical tolerance from a scientific point of view.

Pedagogical tolerance has its own dynamics of development. Based on this, several stages can be shown. For this, first of all, it is necessary to create a clear idea about the structural structure of tolerance. In pedagogy, more attention has been paid to the cognitive, emotional and behavioral components of tolerance.

In the process of pedagogical activity, the cognitive component of tolerance can be seen in the readiness to accept certain views of the students, the results the teacher expects from him, and the manifestation of the student in his own image. If this component of tolerance is not present in the teacher's activity, then a work style that prevents dialogue-based relationships will be formed.

The emotional component of pedagogical tolerance is directly related to the manifestation of empathy in the communication process. In this place, emotional stability and affective tolerance appear as the main form of tolerance. The essence of such tolerance is manifested in the teacher's tolerant attitude to emotional pressures and signals. The affective component of pedagogical tolerance allows the teacher to deeply understand the personal-emotional processes of students' experiences, not to have a bad opinion about them, and to create a favorable situation for them to support them in every way.

The behavioral component of pedagogical tolerance requires the teacher to have a high level of communicative competence.

The personal approach of pedagogical tolerance is manifested in connection with the level of tolerance and values of the teacher. In this place, the teacher's self-acceptance, self-esteem is manifested as his personal tolerance.

Within the framework of the dialogic approach, the teacher's own internal personal conditions are understood. They help students to understand the differences and natural peculiarities. Also, a teacher with a tolerant worldview will be able to see and accept these differences. Teachers with pedagogical tolerance can demonstrate the ability to recognize the rights, freedom, independence, individuality of each student, the ability to live and work together with others, cooperation, and readiness to engage in dialogue processes. Teachers' dialogue with students is an important part of the pedagogical process and one of the complex tasks. Because the effectiveness of the educational process depends on the tolerance of the teacher. Failure to engage in dialogue reduces the possibilities of the subjects of the pedagogical process to achieve results based on feedback. Because they will not have the opportunity to reflect and correct their activities in this situation. In such situations, the teacher and the student work in different formats.

Manifestation of pedagogical tolerance within the framework of a facilitative approach means the development of this activity in the process of higher pedagogical education with the help of pedagogical knowledge. In order to develop professional tolerance in future teachers, attention is paid to its multidirectional nature. The development of pedagogical tolerance in future teachers is a long-term process that is directly related to a number of internal and external factors. It should be emphasized that pedagogical tolerance is not formed, but developed.

There are a number of works on the study of professional tolerance in the theory of pedagogy. Among such works, D.V.Zinoveva's work is devoted to the development of socio-cultural competence of future pedagogues, P.F.Komogorova's formation of tolerance within the interpersonal relations of students, E.G.Vinogradova's study of the psychological content of pedagogical tolerance at the level of the teacher's important professional quality, N.Yu.Kudzieva. It is possible to include studies such as the tolerance of the subjects of the higher professional education process. Also, the research devoted to the use of the possibilities of theatricalization in the formation of tolerant behavior of future teachers is also of special importance.

Experts have tried to theoretically and practically justify the fact that pedagogical tolerance is a special form of general tolerance and is evident in the educational process. It is of particular pedagogical importance that teachers can distinguish the specific aspects of subjects of the educational process according to their personal and social characteristics and have a tolerant attitude towards them.

Above, we tried to show different opinions of experts regarding professional tolerance. It should be emphasized that tolerance is a moral quality of a pedagogue, and it allows to pedagogically describe and support the relationship between the subjects of the educational process, the tolerance of the teacher expressing their principles, the level of understanding of students, and the desire to enter into a dialogue with them. That is why the professional tolerance of the teacher cannot be equated with indifference, inactivity, lack of opinion. Accordingly, tolerance is a professionally important quality of a teacher, which serves to ensure the success of professional activity. In researching the problem of developing pedagogical tolerance in future teachers, taking into account the psychological aspects of the formation of a

tolerant attitude towards students in them, including their gender characteristics, personal qualities, socio-economic status of their living family, values they rely on, mental characteristics, national mentality, the current level of cultural worldviews, it is required to pay attention to spiritual and moral qualities. That is why the development of professional tolerance in future teachers is one of the urgent problems waiting for its solution, and it is evaluated as the main element of professional competence.

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